

BRAIN AND PSYCHE IN PSYCHOLOGY**Mingboev Shohkrukhbek Obidjon's son**

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Annotation: This article focuses on the brain and psychology, which focuses on the most relevant ideas about psychology and the brain. The brain and psychology are one of the most necessary factors for an individual, a form that leads and helps a person to mature perfection. Performs psychological reflection processes. The brain is made up of two parts of it, the right and left brain. Scientists' opinions, their experiences, their research, their conclusions, and their opinions can be seen in the psychology and brain in the main places for an individual.

Keywords: Psychology, body, spirit, matter, nerve, tissue, person, impulse, cell, spirit, organism, conductivity, center, neuropsychologist.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена мозгу и психологии, в которой основное внимание уделяется наиболее актуальным идеям о психологии и мозге. Мозг и психология являются одними из самых необходимых факторов для индивида, формой, которая ведет и помогает человеку созревать к совершенству. Осуществляет процессы психологической рефлексии. Мозг состоит из двух частей: правого и левого полушария. Мнения ученых, их опыт, их исследования, их выводы и их мнения можно увидеть в психологии и мозге в основных местах для человека.

Ключевые слова: Мозг, психология, тело, дух, материя, нерв, ткань, человек, импульс, клетка, дух, организм, проводимость, центр, нейропсихолог.

LOG IN

Psychology is known to be a special property of highly organized matter, which reflects the objective universe in a special way. Psychology (ancient Greek: psychikos) or spirituality is a characteristic of a highly organized matter (brain) that reflects reality in a separate form. It is primarily reflected in intuition, imagination, thinking, willful behavior, and other subjective images. Psychology is secondary to matter. Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to support more than the gecko's body head. Psychology originated at a certain stage of matter development—the emergence of a separate form of sensitivity or the ability to feel in living organisms. The morphological and physiological structure of a living creature was developed in the process of complexity, the formation and development of the nervous system, the formation and improvement of the cerebral cortex, its large hemisphere. A distinct organ of psychology is the cerebral cortex of humans and highly developed animals. Psychology is a unit of objectivity with subjectivity. When it comes to highly organized matter, we understand the brain, which means that the material basis for human and animal psychology is the cerebral cortex, which is the highest part of the central nervous system. But human brains become much more complicated than animals' brains. The human brain is also large in size. If the monkey's brain weighs between 400 and 500 grams, the weight of the human brain is an average of 1400 grams. Brain function is so complex in the body's life that we can also see that the brain accounts for 2% of the weight of the whole body and works more than 18 percent of the oxygen that enters the body. The higher the stage of animal development, the more severe its brain becomes against its body. The weight of the brain is of particular importance in an individual's psychological life. But the structure of the brain is very important. Therefore, it is not right to judge a person's mind based on the weight of the brain. Some people are known to have a much heavier brain weight than the average weight, as well as some people's brain weight on average. The human skull is considered to be an irreversible, complex organ of a person's psychology, consisting of large hemisphere, brain, intermediate brain, middle brain,

and long brain. The cerebral cortex forms a central nervous structure that ensures that all organisms in the human body interact and interact with each other and that the environment is biannual. Much of my psychological activity is made up of several rows, consisting of extremely multi-nerve cells located, and is associated with the functioning of the shell of large hemisphere of the cerebral cortex, which consists of a layer of gray matter. The nervous system is made up of nerve tissue, which in turn consists of the nerve cell. Each nerve cell, or neural nucleus, is made up of a cell consisting of a large number of networked thigh tumors - dendrites and one long tumor - accent. The intermolecular force from all these filaments is enough to support more than thegecko's body weight—even when it is skittering upside down without a globe! A set of nerve cells is made up of the gray matter of the brain, and a clumsy of nerve fibers is the white substance of the brain. Nerve tissue has its own characteristics, which are the main characteristics of arousal and permeability [1].

LITERATURE THE LIST

Russian physiologist P. K. Anoxin (1898-1974), who devoted many years of his life to the problems of unlocking the physiological foundations of psychology, identified the return afferenstation systems, resulting in the separation of movement planning and organs into their own functional organs, known as motion acceptors. In the early 19th century, F. Gall, the founder of frenology as a scientific field, tried to prove that a person's various abilities, even the stronger development of the head bone, were linked to the stronger development of joining, which is found in various nervous tissues on the surface. They observed that my individual psychological function belongs to certain parts of the brain, when it is locally injured. In this way, on the third forehead turn of the left hemisphere, the Broca Center (named after the French anatomy P. Broka, who identified it), and then the Vemike Center, which "manages the understanding of speech" at the back of the upper part of that left hemisphere (called P. Broka), The German psychiatrist who opened it, named after K. Vemike) is separated. A. R. Luria, a renowned neuropsychologist, believes that this is why the task

of "localizing" psychological function in limited areas of the brain "should be replaced by an analysis of the same system of jointly working brain zones that implement this functional system, in other words, how a functional system is intertwined throughout the cerebral cortex, through the appropriate systems.

Psychological processes are a separate properties of the brain and occur only depending on the functioning of the brain. The human skull is a highly external matter, and psychology is the product of this matter, its function. To find out how psychological events occur, you need to study its material basis - connected to the nervous system - because all psychological processes in a person are the result of the functioning of the cerebral and nervous system. No psychological process can be formed on its own, and psychology arises only because of the effects of it or this stimulant on the brain. If the onset of psychology is the effect of the stimulant, its final result is the body's response to the stimulant. Any psychological activity consists only of reflective, reflective activity of the brain. It is known that psychology and consciousness did not suddenly arise, but as a result of a long historical evolution, they were counted, grown, and improved. The development of human psychology is fraught with phloginesis and ontoginosis. Filoginez is that from the time of mankind's emergence to the present day, psychology has been improved from generation to generation. Ontogenesis, on the other hand, is the growth and development of a child's psychology from the day he is born until the end of his or her life. Psychological activity is always unique to a particular entity and is linked to its individual characteristics. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) At the same time, psychology is objective as a real process of the work of the brain, which creates a particular view of the objective universe. Psychology is a visible unit of psychological processes, situations, and human psychological characteristics. A high form of psychological development is human psychology. Its origin and development played a crucial role in the way man interacted with the world around him. Human psychology is the product not only of biological development but also of social development. Social and labor practices have

created a high, only human form of psychology—the awkwardness. The most important feature of human psychology is the ability to foresee things, events, and so on and to plan what it does. A person understands objective predictions and events based on experience. Based on a person's psychological activity, the interaction of the first and second signal systems lies. An important aspect of psychology is its reflective nature, namely, the formation of reflexes, which are continuous and strict about the process. Real psychology exists in the form of activity. In activity, it is formed, displayed, and learned. Education and discipline play an important role in the development of human psychology. (Galatians 5:22, 23) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to answers with you. Psychology studies psychology [2].

RESEARCH METADODOLOGY

In administering the functioning of the internal organs of the sympathetic and parasympathic nervous system, the unique Mantagonists are at odds, bringing the functioning of an organ to the opposite state. For example, if the sympathetic system accelerates heart activity, the parasympathic system slows down. Normal activity of the organism is maintained in a certain "balance" of the sympathetic and parasympathic vegetative nervous system. The vegetative nervous system plays a major role in emotional nightmares. Reticular formation often plays a special role in governing a person's psychological processes, characteristics, and circumstances. Through reticular formation, it is a circular structure that is interconnected with the network of nerve fibers located in the long and subsequent brain in the brain. It affects the electrical well-being of the cerebral cortex, the functional state of the cerebral cortex, the centers of the cerebral cortex, the cerebral cortex, and the cerebral cortex. In scientific psychology, the history of studying the brain as an organ of psychology involves studying the basics of understanding the relationship between organisms and environments that go in two directions and opening up the morphology and function of individual structures of the brain. The introduction of the concept of reflexes into science by R. Decart in the 17th century plays a role as one of the most important

theories in the opening of the foundations of the influence of the organism and the environment. Reflex is the body's response to external and internal influences through the central nervous system. The development of this concept, implemented by I. M. Sechenov (1829-1905), and the fact that this mechanism applies to all psychological processes, leads to the fact that in scientific psychology, the principle of determinism has been gradually confirmed. Highly esteeming reflexes in human life, Sechenov I describes them as follows: "All acts (actions) of intelligent and unconscious life are reflexes according to the method (essence) of origin." In the reflective act I. M. Sechenov separates three sections;

1. In the first joint, the sensing "ball" effect becomes a nerve trigger.
2. Based on the processes of movement and disruption, information processing and decision-making occur in a unique way.
3. Transfer to the organs (muscles and glands, etc.) that carry out the command. Pavlov I (1849-1936) developed the idea of I. M. Sechenov in studying brain reflective activity, introduced new content into the concept of reflexes, and established the basis for the formation of conditional reflexes.

Otherwise, bending consists of a general characteristic of matter, which represents the characteristics and symptoms of objects to a variety of ways of understanding, the relationship and structure of other q a objects. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19 , 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you[3].

There are two types of reflexlamming: unconditional and conditional reflexes. Unconditional reflexes become congenital and begin to manifest themselves from the early days of life and later without any experience (without qualifications). For example, the handshake when the needle is pieced, the separation of the socket when it falls in the mouth cavity of the food.

ANALYZES AND RESULTS

Reflexlamming vary - occurring from the spine and growth of the cerebral cortex, which is attached to the pathways of unconditional reflexes. The area of conditional

reflexlamming yield is the cerebral cortex. The conditional influencer reports on the existence of some event that is important to the body's life, such as the presence of food, the emergence of risk-thrifting. Therefore, I. P. Pavlov called the cerebral cortex activity signal activity. Using the method of conditional reflexes, I. P. Pavlov found that large hemisphere activity in the cerebral cortex consists of the analysis and synthesis processes of many influencers coming from the body's internal environment and the external environment to the nervous system. Analysis and synthesis are performed by I. P. Pavlov using specific nervous systems called analyzers. Analyzers are a nerve physiological apparatus consisting of a nerve ending (receptor) in the periphery, a sensory nerve (transmission pathway) and an area of the brain shell that receives the corresponding stimulant. I. P. Pavlov's theory about the first and second signal systems is of great importance to scientific psychology. All things for animals are signaled by influencers in large hemisphere and their traces, which come directly to the body's visual and hearing receptors. This is the first signal system, common in humans and animals. Words form the second, special human signal system. The words were called "signal signals" by P. Pavlov for replacing the signal laming coming from things and events. The functioning of the second signal system goes directly related, not separated from the first signal system. The second signal system is the physiological basis for thought and speech. An important disadvantage in explaining the basics of psychological activity using the classical concept of reflexes is that the reflex system does not explain the role of human psychology as governing and changing. I. P. Pavlov's disciples and followers sought to solve this deficiency by changing the concept of a reflective organic system to the concept of a reflective ring system.

SUMMARIES

In conclusion, the functional structure of the human brain is divided into three blocks: l-block - an energy block, which provides the tone for normal functioning of the cerebral cortex. The structure of the reflective circle on the brain Berstein is located

at the top of the pouch. Block 2 is a block for receiving, processing, and storing information (located on the back of both hemisphere with upper bone and below parts). Block 3 - provides programming, managing and controlling activities (located on the forehead). Important differences are observed in the functional system of the human and animal brain. At a time when both hemisphere of the animal is of the same value, the human left hemisphere is dominant (dominant) in a person, and the right hemisphere is subject to it, and it is connected to the leading role of the right hand (such dominance or extinguishes in the left, or passes through the right hemisphere). In the hemisphere of the left brain are speech centers associated with the management of complex forms of a person's behavior and activity. The resulting embryo was allowed to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it implanted. Based on the accumulated scientific information, it can be noted that the left brain hemisphere is differentiated from the work of the right hemisphere of the brain

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